

Cases referred to the Grand Chamber

Two cases have been referred to the Grand Chamber of the European Court of Human Rights.

At its last meeting (4 October 2010), the Grand Chamber panel of five judges decided to refer the cases **S. H. and Others v. Austria** and **Nejdet Şahin and Perihan Şahin v. Turkey** and to reject requests to refer 87 other cases¹.

Referrals accepted

[S. H. and Others v. Austria \(no.57813/00\)](#)

The applicants are two married couples from Austria. Suffering from infertility and wishing to use medically-assisted procreation, they complained about the prohibition of sperm and ova donation for in vitro fertilisation in domestic law.

In its judgment of 1 April 2010, the Court held, by a majority, that there had been a violation of Article 14 (prohibition of discrimination) in conjunction with Article 8 (right to respect for family life) of the European Convention on Human Rights. On 4 October 2010 the case was referred to the Grand Chamber at the Austrian Government's request.

[Nejdet Sahin and Perihan Sahin v. Turkey \(application no.13279/05\)](#)

The applicants, Nejdet Şahin and Perihan Şahin, are two Turkish nationals whose son, an army pilot, died in May 2001 in a plane crash which occurred during the transport of troops from Diyarbakır to Ankara. They applied unsuccessfully for the monthly pension payable to family members under the Anti-Terrorism Act. They complained that the subsequent proceedings before the military administrative courts had been unfair on account of the alleged disparity between the restrictive approach taken by those courts in the matter and the rulings of the ordinary administrative courts, which accepted that the Anti-Terrorism Act should be applicable to the families of soldiers who had died in the same accident.

In its judgment of 27 May 2010, the Court held, by six votes to one, that there had been no violation of Article 6 § 1 (right to a fair hearing) of the European Convention on Human Rights. On 4 October 2010 the case was referred to the Grand Chamber at the applicants' request.

Requests for referral rejected

The judgments in the following 87 cases are now final²

¹ Under Article 43 of the European Convention on Human Rights, within three months from the date of a Chamber judgment, any party to the case may, in exceptional cases, request that the case be referred to the 17-member Grand Chamber of the Court. In that event, a panel of five judges considers whether the case raises a serious question affecting the interpretation or application of the Convention or its protocols, or a serious issue of general importance, in which case the Grand Chamber will deliver a final judgment. If no such question or issue arises, the panel will reject the request, at which point the judgment becomes final. Otherwise Chamber judgments become final on the expiry of the three-month period or earlier if the parties declare that they do not intend to make a request to refer.

Berhani v. Albania (no. **847/05**); judgment of 27.05.2010

Mamikonyan v. Armenia (no. **25083/05**); judgment of 16.03.2010

Frodl v. Austria (no. **20201/04**); judgment of 08.04.2010

Fatullayev v. Azerbaijan (no. **40984/07**); judgment of 22.04.2010

Poncelet v. Belgium (no. **44418/07**); judgment of 30.03.2010

Đokić v. Bosnia and Herzegovina (no. **6518/04**); judgment of 27.05.2010

Kvartuč v. Croatia (N° 2) (no. **34830/07**); judgment of 22.04.2010

Crabtree v. Czech Republic (no. **41116/04**); judgment of 04.05.2010
Macready v. Czech Republic (nos. **4824/06 and 15512/08**); judgment of 22.04.2010

Ruokanen and others v. Finland (no. **45130/06**); judgment of 06.04.2010

Fleury v. France (no. **29784/06**); judgment of 11.05.2010

Stefanou v. Greece (no. **2954/07**); judgment of 22.04.2010

Brignoli and others v. Italy (nos. **19877/03, 32969/02, 18359/03 and 18363/03**); judgment of 18.05.2010

Villa v. Italy (no. **19675/06**); judgment of 20.04.2010

Petrenco v. Moldova (no. **20928/05**); judgment of 30.03.2010
Vetrenko v. Moldova (no. **36552/02**); judgment of 18.05.2010

Adamczuk v. Poland (no. **30523/07**); judgment of 17.07.2008

Adamkiewicz v. Poland (no. **54729/00**); judgment of 02.03.2010

Avellar Cordeiro Zagallo v. Portugal (no. **30844/05**); judgment of 08.06.2010

Stegarescu and Bahrin v. Portugal (no. **46194/06**); judgment of 06.04.2010

Ana Pavel v. Romania (no. **4503/06**); judgment of 16.03.2010
Băcilă v. Romania (no. **19234/04**); judgment of 30.03.2010
Cenoiu and others v. Romania (no. **26036/02**); judgment of 02.03.2010
Popa and Alecsandru v. Romania (no. **2617/04**); judgment of 23.03.2010
R.R. v. Romania (n° 1) (no. **1188/05**); judgment of 10.11.2010
Răcăreanu v. Romania (no. **14262/03**); judgment of 01.06.2010
SC Vălie Prod SRL v. Romania (no. **23507/04**); judgment of 23.03.2010
Stomff v. Romania (no. **39312/07**); judgment of 02.03.2010

Abayeva and others v. Russia (no. **37542/05**); judgment of 08.04.2010
Abdurashidova v. Russia (no. **32968/05**); judgment of 08.04.2010
Akhmetov v. Russia (no. **37463/04**); judgment of 01.04.2010
Alapayevy v. Russia (no. **39676/06**); judgment of 03.06.2010

2 Under Article 44 § 2 (c) of the European Convention on Human Rights, the judgment of a Chamber becomes final when the panel of the Grand Chamber rejects the request to refer under Article 43.

Aliyeva v. Russia (no. 1901/05); judgment of 18.02.2010
Artyomov v. Russia (no. 14146/02); judgment of 27.05.2010
Bezmyanny v. Russia (no. 10941/03); judgment of 08.04.2010
Bik v. Russia (no. 26321/03); judgment of 22.04.2010
Bulychev v. Russia (no. 24086/04); judgment of 08.04.2010
Denisova and Moiseyeva v. Russia (no. 16903/03); judgment of 01.04.2010
Dzhabrailov v. Russia (no. 3678/06); judgment of 20.05.2010
Georgiy Nikolayevich Mikhaylov v. Russia (no. 4543/04); judgment of 01.04.2010
Goroshchenya v. Russia (no. 38711/03); judgment of 22.04.2010
Ilyasova v. Russia (no. 26966/06); judgment of 10.06.2010
Khatuyeva v. Russia (no. 12463/05); judgment of 22.04.2010
Khaydarov v. Russia (no. 21055/09); judgment of 20.05.2010
Khodzhayev v. Russia (no. 52466/08); judgment of 12.05.2010
Khutsayev and others v. Russia (no. 16622/05); judgment of 27.05.2010
Klein v. Russia (no. 24268/08); judgment of 01.04.2010
Konashevskaya and others v. Russia (no. 3009/07); judgment of 03.06.2010
Korolev v. Russia (n° 2) (no. 5447/03); judgment of 01.04.2010
Kouzmin v. Russia (no. 58939/00); judgment of 18.03.2010
Mutayeva v. Russia (no. 43418/06); judgment of 22.04.2010
Mudayevy v. Russia (no. 33105/05); judgment of 08.04.2010
Mutsolgova and others v. Russia (no. 2952/06); judgment of 01.04.2010
Pavlenko v. Russia (no. 42371/02); judgment of 01.04.2010
Tasatayevy v. Russia (no. 37541/05); judgment of 08.04.2010
Tronin v. Russia (no. 24461/02); judgment of 18.03.2010
Tupchiyeva v. Russia (no. 37461/05); judgment of 22.04.2010
Tovsultanova v. Russia (no. 26974/06); judgment of 17.06.2010
Sadulayeva v. Russia (no. 38570/05); judgment of 08.04.2010
Seriyevy v. Russia (no. 20201/05); judgment of 08.04.2010
Sevastyanov v. Russia (no. 37024/02); judgment of 22.04.2010
Shakhabova v. Russia (no. 39685/06); judgment of 12.05.2010
Smetanko v. Russia (no. 6239/04); judgment of 29.04.2010
Suleymanova v. Russia (no. 9191/06); judgment of 12.05.2010
Umalatov and others v. Russia (no. 8345/05); judgment of 08.04.2010
Vakayeva and others v. Russia (no. 2220/05); judgment of 10.06.2010
Yershova v. Russia (no. 1387/04); judgment of 08.04.2010

Ahmet Arslan and others v. Turkey (no. 41135/98); judgment of 23.02.2010

Asproftas v. Turkey and Petrakidou v. Turkey (nos. 16079/90 and 16081/90); judgment of 27.05.2010

Gökhan Yıldırım v. Turkey (no. 31950/05); judgment of 23.02.2010

Kemal Taşkin and others v. Turkey (nos. 30206/04, 37038/04, 43681/04, 45376/04, 12881/05, 28697/05, 32797/05 and 45609/05); judgment of 02.02.2010

Orhan Çaçan v. Turkey (no. 26437/04); judgment of 23.03.2010

Sarica and Dilaver v. Turkey (no. 11765/05); judgment of 27.05.2010

Şerefli and others v. Turkey (N° 2) (no. 14015/05); judgment of 30.03.2010

Kin-Stib et Majkić v. Serbia (no. 12312/05); judgment of 20.04.2010

Kocianová v. Slovakia (no. 21692/06); judgment of 18.05.2010

Handölsdalen Sami Village and others v. Sweden (no. 39013/04); judgment of 30.03.2010

Calabrò v. Ukraine (no. 17426/02); judgment of 23.03.2010

Feldman v. Ukraine (nos. 76556/01 and 38779/04); judgment of 08.04.2010

Galat v. Ukraine (no. 716/05); judgment of 20.05.2010

Lopatin and Medvedskiy v. Ukraine (nos. 2278/03 and 6222/03); judgment of 20.05.2010

Menshakova v. Ukraine (no. 377/02); judgment of 08.04.2010

Shaposhnikov v. Ukraine (no. 30853/04); judgment of 08.04.2010

Ukraine-Tyumen v. Ukraine (no. 22603/02); judgment of 20.05.2010

Al-Saadoon and Mufdhi v. the United-Kingdom (no. 61498/08); judgment of 02.03.2010

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The European Court of Human Rights was set up in Strasbourg by the Council of Europe Member States in 1959 to deal with alleged violations of the 1950 European Convention on Human Rights.